

THE EFFECT OF PROACTIVE PERSONALITY AND LOCUS OF CONTROL ON INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF WORK ENGAGEMENT

Mehmet TEKELİ * & Aziz Gökhan ÖZKOÇ **

Abstract

The aim of the study is to test the mediating role of work engagement on the effects of proactive personality and locus of control characteristics on innovative work behaviors of the employees. A field study was conducted, and the research data were collected using the questionnaire technique for an empirical analysis of the structural equation modeling created for this purpose. The research population has consisted of employees working in food and beverage departments of hotel businesses, where complex and complicated activities are carried out, therefore a high amount of qualified workforce is needed. According to the results obtained in the results of the survey applied to the employees who provide services in the food and beverage department of the hotels located in Antalya province, which is one of the most important tourist destinations in Turkey. Employees' proactive personality characteristics and their level of commitment positively affect their tendency to show innovative entrepreneurial behavior; proactive personality and internal locus of control had a positive and significant effect on work engagement; however, the mediating effect of external locus of control on innovative entrepreneurial behavior was not detected as significant.

Keywords: Proactive Personality; Locus of Control; Innovative Work Behavior; Work Engagement; Food and Beverage Employees.

O EFEITO DA PERSONALIDADE PRÓATIVA E LOCUS DE CONTROLE NO COMPORTAMENTO INOVADOR DO TRABALHO: O PAPEL MEDIADOR DO ENGAJAMENTO NO TRABALHO

Resumo

O objetivo do estudo é testar o efeito mediador do engajamento no trabalho sobre o efeito de traços de personalidade proativos e locus de controle sobre comportamentos empresariais inovadores. Um estudo de campo foi realizado e os dados foram coletados através da técnica de levantamento a fim de analisar a nível empírico o modelo de equação estrutural criado para este fim. O universo da pesquisa é formado por empregados que prestam serviços em departamentos de alimentos e bebidas de empresas hoteleiras, onde atividades complexas e complicadas são desenvolvidas, exigindo uma grande necessidade de mão-de-obra qualificada. De acordo com os resultados obtidos nos resultados da pesquisa aplicada aos empregados que prestam serviços no departamento de alimentos e bebidas dos hotéis localizados na província de Antalya, que é um dos destinos turísticos mais importantes da Turquia, as características de personalidade proativa dos Empregados e seu nível de comprometimento afetam positivamente sua tendência de mostrar um comportamento empreendedor inovador; a personalidade pró-ativa e o local de controle interno tiveram um efeito positivo e significativo no engajamento no trabalho; entretanto, o efeito mediador do locus de controle externo sobre o comportamento empresarial inovador não foi detectado como significativo.

Palavras-chave: Personalidade Pró-ativa; Locus de Controle; Comportamento Inovador do Trabalho; Engajamento no Trabalho, Empregados de Alimentos e Bebidas.

EL EFECTO DE LA PERSONALIDAD PROACTIVA Y EL LOCUS DE CONTROL EN EL COMPORTAMIENTO LABORAL INNOVADOR EL PAPEL MEDIADOR DEL COMPROMISO LABORAL

Resumen

El objetivo del estudio es comprobar el efecto mediador del compromiso laboral en el efecto de las características de personalidad proactivas y el locus orientado al control sobre los comportamientos empresariales innovadores. Se realizó un estudio de campo y los datos se recolectaron mediante la técnica de encuesta con el fin de analizar en nivel empírica el modelo de ecuaciones estructurales creado a tal efecto. El universo de la investigación está formado por empleados que dan servicios en departamentos de alimentación y bebidas de negocios hoteleros, donde se desarrollan actividades complejas y complicadas que requiere una alta necesidad de mano de obra cualificada. Según los resultados obtenidos en la encuesta aplicada a los empleados que prestan servicios en el departamento de alimentos y bebidas de hoteles situados en la provincia de Antalya, que es uno de los destinos turísticos más importantes de Turquia, las características de personalidad proactiva de los empleados y su nivel de compromiso afectan positivamente a su tendencia a mostrar un comportamiento empresarial innovador; la personalidad proactiva y el locus de control interno tuvieron un efecto positivo y significativo sobre el compromiso laboral; sin embargo, no se detectó que el efecto mediador del locus de control externo sobre el comportamiento empresarial innovador fuera significativo.

Palabras clave: Personalidad Proactiva; Locus de Control; Comportamiento Laboral Innovador; Compromiso Laboral, Empleados de Alimentos y Bebidas.

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*Ph.D of Tourism Management (Nevşehir Hacı Bektaş Veli University, 2021). Master in Tourism Management (Nevşehir Hacı Bektaş Veli University, 2016). Bachelor's Degree in Tourism Management (Nevşehir Hacı Bektaş Veli University, 2014). Doctor and independent researcher. CV: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6069-4740> [tekelimehmet@hotmail.com]

**Ph.D of Management and Organization (Sakarya University, 2009). Master in Tourism Management (Sakarya, 2006). Bachelor's Degree in Tourism and Hotel Management (Erciyes University, 2003). Associate Professor at Sakarya University. CV: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8420-8228> [azizozkoc@subu.edu.tr]

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1 INTRODUCTION

In today's innovation age, it has become more significant for businesses to rule the dynamic changes in their environment with innovative ideas and activities rather than to follow these changes (Niesen, Van Hootegeem, Vander Elst, Battistelli & De Witte, 2018; Torres, Espinosa, Dornberger & Acosta, 2017).

Enterprises' abilities to take and implement innovative decisions on a sectoral basis is under the influence of many factors inside and outside the business (Weiermair, 2004). In enterprises having achieved a leading position in their sector thanks to their innovative work processes, one of the main actors of this success is the qualified labor force resource (Scott & Bruce, 1994).

The innovative attributes and tendencies of the employees, who have become a key force in acquiring and putting knowledge into practice and qualified as "intellectual capital," have become one of the main determinants of the customer-oriented quality production and service understanding.

Every employee working in the business does not have the same tendency to innovatively think and act. The personal and managerial factors that cause the differentiation of innovative work behaviors on an individual basis have been discussed and investigated in different dimensions in the literature so far.

In this context, employees' tendencies to show innovative work behavior were correlated and analyzed with some management factors such as leadership (Yidong & Xinxin, 2013; Afsar, Badir & Saeed, 2014), organizational climate (Shanker, Bhanugopan, Van der Heijden & Farrell, 2017; Imran, Saeed, Anis-Ul-Haq & Fatima, 2010), organizational justice (Kim & Park, 2017), leader-member interaction (Saeed, Afsar, Cheema & Javed, 2019), and some personal factors such as self-efficacy (Hsiao, Chang, Tu, Chen, 2011), cultural intelligence (Korzilius, Bücken & Beerlage, 2017), overqualification (Kaymakçı & Görener, 2019) and personality (Li, Liu, Liu & Wang, 2017; Tabak, Erkuş & Meydan, 2010).

The subject of this study is to address the concepts of proactive personality, locus of control, and work engagement that can affect employees' innovative work behavior tendencies.

This research aims to define the effects of proactive personality traits and locus of control on innovative work behaviors and to determine the level of mediating role of work engagement in this interaction.

When the theoretical and empirical studies conducted on the variables subject to the research so far are examined, it is seen that the binary interactions between variables have been handled in the context of cause-effect relationships, while no study has been

encountered dealing with all four variables with a holistic perspective and with the help of Structural Equation Modeling.

From a managerial perspective, it is predicted that the findings and evaluations obtained as the research results can contribute to managers in three different perspectives. It is known that managers can create an innovative corporate culture if they are assisted by a qualified labor force.

Therefore, in selecting and directing employees who can show Innovative Work Behavior, findings will be evaluated how much the candidates' proactive personality features and locus of control perceptions could be a criterion of determination. Secondly, the rationality level of training programs prepared for employees working in businesses to develop their perceptions about proactive personality traits and locus of control will be discussed to generate innovative ideas and implement them. Finally, it will be determined to what extent managers can have an impact on the realization of innovative ideas and practices they expect from their employees through enabling them to dedicate themselves to their work.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

2.1 Proactive Personality and Innovative Work Behavior

Proactive personality, whose theoretical infrastructure is based on the "Interactionism Approach" within the scope of social learning theory, is defined as the personality of individuals who have relatively stable behavioral tendencies and use them until they realize the change in their environment (Bateman & Crant, 1993).

Proactive individuals believe that they can change the conditions around them as a result of their behavior. These people can realize the opportunities they encounter and can take the initiative by identifying opportunities. With these features, proactive individuals try to influence and change their environment (Bateman & Crant, 1993; Crant, 2000).

Based on the five-factor personality model, to explore which personality traits are more likely to exhibit innovative behaviors in the workplace, many studies have been done lately. However, it has been stated that the five-factor personality model is not specially designed for individuals in the business area.

On the other hand, it is emphasized that additional personality structures such as proactive personality should be taken into consideration while examining the personality features that determine innovative work behavior.

Accordingly, it has been suggested that proactive personality has significantly more validity in predicting innovative behaviors than five-factor personality traits (Li et al., 2017; Seibert, Kraimer & Crant, 2001; Thomas, Whitman & Viswesvaran, 2010).

In this direction, studies on the relationship between proactive personality and innovative work behavior have revealed that proactive personality positively affects innovative work behavior (Giebels, de Reuver, Rispens & Ufkes 2016; Kale, 2019; Ng & Feldman, 2013; Pelenk, 2018). In light of this information, the H₁ hypothesis has been developed as follows.

H₁: Employees' proactive personality features positively affect the innovative work behavior.

2.2 Locus of Control and Innovative Work Behavior

The concept of locus of control presented by Julian Rotter within the scope of social learning theory is defined as "a personality attribute" and "the tendency of individuals to perceive positive or negative events affecting them as a result of their behavior or as occurring under the influence of external forces such as luck, fortune, and fate." (Rotter, 1966: 1).

The locus of control concept is handled in two dimensions as internal and external locus of control. The tendency to perceive the events under his control is defined as the internal locus of control, while the tendency to perceive under the external forces is defined as the external locus of control (Rotter, 1966).

In social learning theory, how the information obtained through environment and experiences is used and how it affects behavior are associated with cognitive abilities. In this direction, locus of control is where different behavioral styles arise from perceptual differences in individuals (Rotter, 1966).

Therefore, the internal locus of control or external locus of control can cause individuals to behave differently. It is emphasized that the individuals with an internal locus of control who believe that they can organize the events around themselves will introduce more innovative attributes than those who with the external locus of control interpreting the events around them to luck, fate, and other external factors (Engle, Mah & Sadri, 1997).

The internal locus of control is suggested as a positive personality characteristic, strengthening the individuals' entrepreneurial properties and directing them to innovative behavior (Basım & Şeşen, 2008). It is stated that the internal locus of control positively affects innovative work behaviors (Miller, Kets De Vries & Toulouse, 1982; Rum, 2012; Tabak et al., 2010; Töre & Yolal, 2017), whereas the External Locus of Control

affects negatively (Kale, 2019). In this direction, H₂ and H₃ hypotheses were developed within the scope of the research.

H₂: Internal locus of control positively affects employees' innovative work behavior.

H₃: External locus of control negatively affects employees' innovative work behavior.

2.3 Work Engagement and Innovative Work Behavior

Work engagement is defined as "is a positive mental state for work, and a state of vigor, dedication, and absorption related to work." The work engagement's *vigor dimension* identifies the individual's high-level energy and mental endurance in the work environment; *dedication dimension* identifies the individual's strong involvement in the work with the emotions of excitement, enthusiasm, inspiration, pride, struggle, and meaningfulness; *absorption dimension* identifies the individual's full focus and fulfillment of job roles (Schaufeli, Salanova, González-Romá & Bakker, 2002: 74).

According to the Job Demands-Resources model, as a result of work engagement, it is argued that such performance increases will occur in employees such as in-role performance, additional role behavior, creativity, etc. (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008). Similarly, Bakker (2017) states that work engagement plays a significant role in the emergence of positive organizational outcomes such as creativity and innovation, customer satisfaction, positive financial results, and reduced absenteeism.

Dedicated employees can exhibit supplementary and innovative behaviors for better service performance. In other words, work engagement is observed as an incentive force that affects innovative work behaviors (Garg & Dhar, 2017). Studies in different fields indicated that dedication positively affects innovative work behaviors (Kim & Koo, 2017; Koch, Binnewies & Dormann, 2015; Köroğlu, 2018; Orth & Volmer, 2017; Rao, 2016). In this direction, the H₄ hypothesis developed within the research is as follows:

H₄: Work engagement positively affects employees' innovative work behaviors.

2.4 Work Engagement's Mediating Role

The findings obtained as research results represent that the proactive personality and the locus of control are among the personal resources that can

affect work engagement. Eventually, it is stated that personality attributes are efficient on work engagement and work engagement contributes to positive results (Christian, Garza & Slaughter, 2011).

It is argued that proactive personality is a significant individual factor that directs the employees' behavior to positive situational changes in organizations. Based on this opinion, it is stated that proactive personality positively affects work engagement (Caniels, Semeijn & Renders, 2017; Dijkers, Jansen, de Lange, Vinkenburg & Kooij 2010; Uncuoğlu Yolcu, 2017; Wang, Zhang, Thomas, Yu & Spitzmueller, 2017; Yang, Yan, Fan & Luo, 2017). Accordingly, the H₅ hypothesis was developed.

H₅: A proactive personality positively affects work engagement.

It is claimed that the locus of control, which is supposed to be among personal resources, is one of the variables that best explain work engagement and that the internal locus of control positively affects work engagement (Bejerholm & Eklund, 2007). In their study, Van der Merwe (2003) has determined that the internal locus of control is positively associated with vigor, dedication, and absorption; moreover, the external locus of control is negatively correlated with vigor.

Besides, when the empirical studies are examined, it is seen that the locus of control affects the work engagement (Betoret, 2013; Chukwuorji, Ituma & Ugwu, 2018; Duve, 2015; Sharma & Sharma, 2015). Eventually, H₆ and H₇ hypotheses have been proposed.

H₆: Internal locus of control positively affects work engagement.

H₇: External locus of control negatively affects work engagement.

When the relevant literature is examined, it is seen that work engagement has been discussed in the context of the relationship between mediating role and outcome variables such as the extra-role performance (Salanova, Lorente, Chambel & Martinez, 2011), job performance (Wang, Lu & Siu, 2014), job skill (Airila et al., 2014), service quality (Wang & Tseng, 2019).

Finally, the H₈, H₉, and H₁₀ hypotheses created to determine the work engagement's mediating role in the effect of proactive personality and locus of control on the innovative work behavior are given below. Besides, the proposed research model in line with the determined hypotheses is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Model. Source: Own elaboration.

H₈: Work engagement has a mediating role in the effect of the proactive personality on innovative work behavior.

H₉: Work engagement has a mediating role in the effect of the internal locus of control on innovative work behavior.

H₁₀: Work engagement has a mediating role in the effect of the external locus of control on innovative work behavior.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Sample and procedure

The research population is food and beverage department employees at five-star hotels in Antalya province, Turkey. In this study, the reason why five-star hotels in Antalya have been preferred is that this region is a significant destination for tourism, and the management and organizational structures of these hotels are appropriate for the conduct of the research.

According to the information obtained from Antalya Culture and Tourism Provincial Directorate, there were 341 five-star hotels having tourism management licenses in Antalya in 2019.

The convenience sampling method was used to collect the data. In cases where the population cannot be defined, a 384 sample size is considered sufficient (Gürbüz & Şahin, 2018; www.surveysystem.com, 2021). The researchers administered surveys in a face-to-face interview in August and September 2019.

To reduce common method bias (CMB), the procedural remedies offered by Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Lee & Podsakoff (2003) were used. In this respect, all employees were informed that participation in the study was voluntary; answers in the survey were neither right nor wrong and were going to be used anonymously for academic research purposes.

Additionally, the employees were asked to fill out the questionnaires in a different area from the hotel and off the working hours. The researchers delivered all questionnaires to each participant in envelopes and requested the participants to keep their replies secret.

Although 550 questionnaires were delivered to the hotels' employees who voluntarily agreed to participate in the study, 432 questionnaires completed were returned.

In the study, 59.3% of the 432 employees participating were male, and 40.7% were female employees. Similarly, 59.3% of the employees were single, and 40.7% were married. 55.6% of the participants were between 18-25 years old, and 52.5% were high school graduates. Besides, 40.7% of the participants were in the sector for 1-5 years, and 46.1% were in the current business less than one year

3.2 Measures

In measuring the food and beverage workers' proactive personalities, "The Abbreviated proactive personality scale" (10-item), developed by Bateman and Crant (1993), and revised by Claes, Beheydt, and Lemmens (2005) were used. In measuring the internal-external locus of control, the "work locus of control scale" prepared by Spector (1988) to measure the employees' control focus in business life was used.

The scale consists of eight items measuring the internal locus of control and the external locus of control (shell.cas.usf.edu, 2019). The one-dimensional innovative behavior scale (6-item) created by Scott and Bruce (1994) was used to measure the innovative behaviors of the employees.

To determine the employees' work engagement levels, the short form (9-item) of "the (17-item) Utrecht work dedication scale (UWES) developed by Schaufeli et al. (2002), which was shortened by Schaufeli,

Bakker, and Salanova (2006), was used. All of the scales used consisted of 5-Likert type scales. The experts granted assists in translating scales from English to Turkish.

3.3 Data Analysis Procedure

The data were analyzed with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) software programs. The normal distribution assumption of the data was tested before analyzing and testing the hypotheses.

George and Mallery (2010) state that the data show a normal distribution when the skewness and kurtosis values are between ± 2 . As a result of the analysis, it was understood that the data had skewness and kurtosis values within the ± 2 values range, and the data distribution met the normality assumption.

Abbreviations for variables were expressed as "PP = Proactive Personality, LC = Locus of Control, I-LC = Internal Locus of Control, E-LC = External Locus of Control, IWB = Innovative Work Behavior, WE = Work Engagement"

The present study followed Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) two-step approach to test the proposed model in Figure 1. Firstly, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was carried out to evaluate the measurement model.

Secondly, the proposed structural model and hypothesis developed based on the literature review were tested with structural equation modeling (SEM) (De Leon & Delgado, 2021; Iqbal, 2020). The significance of the mediating role was evaluated according to the bootstrapping result.

Two structural models were used to test the hypotheses. The first model consisted of direct effects of the proactive personality, locus of control, and innovative work behavior (H_1, H_2, H_3), and while the second involved the mediator variable (interaction term), to test the mediating effect of work engagement in these relationships ($H_4, H_5, H_6, H_7, H_8, H_9, H_{10}$).

4 FINDINGS

4.1 Measurement Model: Validity and Reliability of Scales

Firstly, exploratory factor analysis was performed for the scales used in the research. As a result of the EFA, anticipated factors related to the internal locus of control, external locus of control, innovative work behavior, and work engagement scales were formed. However, three items related to the proactive personality scale were excluded due to inappropriate

distribution and low factor loadings (Factor loading \leq 0.30).

Table 1 shows the results of the measurement model. The CFA results obtained by the maximum likelihood calculation method show that the data are

compatible with the model ($\chi^2/df=2,6$, $TLI=0,91$, $IFI=0,93$, $CFI=0,93$, $RMSEA=0,06$, $GFI=0,90$). Therefore, it can be said that the factor structures suggested in the measurement model are supported by data.

Table 1. Results of the measurement model.

Dimensions	Items	Factor loading	C.R.
PP	PP1	652	8,330*
	PP2	617	8,919*
	PP3	709	9,570*
	PP4	704	9,478*
	PP5	726	9,674*
	PP6	663	9,264*
	PP7	501	-a
I-LC	I-LC1	687	10,048*
	I-LC2	743	12,129*
	I-LC3	726	11,968*
	I-LC4	680	-a
E-LC	E-LC1	671	10,691*
	E-LC2	786	11,552*
	E-LC3	686	10,853*
	E-LC4	633	-a
IWB	IWB1	815	11,689*
	IWB2	839	11,850*
	IWB3	437	7,635*
	IWB4	636	10,077*
	IWB5	644	10,174*
	IWB6	562	-a
WE	WE1	599	8,442*
	WE2	639	8,752*
	WE3	605	8,516*
	WE4	564	8,170*
	WE5	712	9,220*
	WE6	519	7,765*
	WE7	683	9,049*
	WE8	581	10,695*
	WE9	494	-a

Note: * $p \leq 0.001$.

As a result of the reliability analysis of the scales, "proactive personality ($\alpha=.83$), internal locus of control ($\alpha=.77$), external locus of control ($\alpha=.78$), innovative work behavior ($\alpha=.83$), work engagement ($\alpha=.84$)" scales can be said to have high-reliability levels (Table

2). The correlation analysis results, which reveal the severity and direction of the relationship between the variables after the validity and reliability analysis, are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Correlation, Reliability, Mean and Standard Deviation Values.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	α	M	SD
PP (1)	1				,83	4,23	0,48
I-LC (2)	,475*	1			,77	4,28	0,50
E-LC (3)	-,214*	-,060	1		,78	1,57	0,44
IWB (4)	,597*	,335*	-,183*	1	,83	4,13	0,51
WE (5)	,512*	,436*	-,155*	,541*	,84	4,19	0,46

Note: * $p \leq 0.001$, (2-Tailed). N=432.

As a result of the correlation analysis, positive and significant relationships were determined between the variables of internal locus of control, proactive

personality, innovative work behavior, and work engagement.

On the other hand, there were negative and significant relationships between external locus of

control, proactive personality, innovative work behavior, and work engagement variables. Besides, proactive personality, internal locus of control, innovative work behavior, and work engagement level of the employees were high, but the level of external locus of control was low (Table 2).

The traditional approach and the contemporary approach are two main approaches to test the mediating role (Gürbüz, 2019). Studies conducted in recent years significantly criticized the traditional method. Some of the criticisms brought to the traditional approach are to decide on the mediating effect as a result of three different supporting hypotheses, the controversy on the terms of "full mediating" and "partial mediating," and the strictness and low reliability of the Sobel test (Gürbüz, 2019; Hayes, 2017). In this context, the mediating effect of work engagement was tested based on the contemporary approach and using SEM. Two different models were used to analyze the mediating role.

The fit index values of the first model established to test the mediating role ($\chi^2/df=3,1$, TLI=0,91, IFI=0,93, CFI=0,93, RMSEA=0,07, GFI=0,89) showed that the proposed model was compatible with the data. After determining the fit, the significance of the relationships between variables was checked, and the effects of proactive personality, internal locus of control, and external locus of control on innovative work behavior were examined.

According to the results of the analysis, the proactive personality affected the innovative work behavior ($p<0,001$; $\beta=,341$) positively, while the external locus of control affected the innovative work

behavior ($p<0,05$; $\beta=-,097$) negatively. On the other hand, a significant effect ($p\geq 0,05$) of the internal locus of control on innovative work behavior was not detected (Table 4). Hence, H₁ and H₃ were accepted, and H₂ was rejected.

The fit index values for the second model established to test the mediating role ($\chi^2/df=2,9$, TLI=0,90, IFI=0,92, CFI=0,92, RMSEA=0,07, GFI=0,86) showed that the proposed model was compatible with the data. After determining the fit, the significance of the relationships between the variables was checked, and Beta values were checked. The significance and Beta values of the second model are shown in Table 4.

Accordingly, a positive and significant effect of proactive personality ($p<0,001$; $\beta=,357$) and internal locus of control ($p<0,001$; $\beta=,383$) on work engagement was determined. In this case, H₄ and H₅ hypotheses were accepted. However, the external locus of control did not have a significant effect on work engagement ($p> 0,05$). Therefore, the H₆ hypothesis was rejected. Finally, work engagement positively affects the innovative work behavior ($p<0,001$; $\beta=,420$) (Table 4).

When examining the variance rates of innovative work behavior and work engagement, it was observed that proactive personality, internal locus of control, and external locus of control explained 68% of innovative work behavior and 28% of work engagement. To determine the mediating role of the work engagement, the total, direct and indirect effects were observed, and according to the bootstrapping test result, the significance was measured (Table 3).

Table 3. Total, Direct and Indirect Effects, and Bootstrapping Confidence Intervals for Indirect Effects.

	Total Effects			Direct Effects			Indirect Effects			
	PP	I-LC	E-LC	PP	I-LC	E-LC	PP	I-LC	E-LC	
IWB	,736	,084	-,087	,586	-,077	-,049	,150	,161	-,038	
WE	,357	,383	-,090	,357	,383	-,090	,000	,000	,000	
		Lower Bounds			Upper Bounds					
	PP	I-LC	E-LC	PP	I-LC	E-LC				
IWB	,083	,095	-,091	,224	,232	,012				
WE	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000				

The study used the bootstrapping coefficient obtained from the bootstrapping method performed through 5,000 samplings and a 95% confidence interval to determine whether the indirect effects of the mediating model were significant or not. In the

bootstrapping method, it was understood that there was a meaningful effect when the lower and upper limits of confidence intervals did not contain zero (Preacher & Hayes, 2008).

Table 4. The Results of the structural model.

Hypothesis	Relation	Path coefficients	C.R.	Decision
Direct effects (Model-1)				
H ₁	IWB ← PP	,712	8,577*	Supported
H ₂	IWB ← I-LC	,053	1,197	Rejected

H ₃	IWB ← E-LC	-.097	-2,097**	Supported
Interaction effects (Model-2)				
H ₄	WE ← PP	,357	5,238*	Supported
H ₅	WE ← I-LC	,383	5,946*	Supported
H ₆	WE ← E-LC	-.090	-1,644	Rejected
H ₇	IWB ← WE	,420	6,295*	Supported
H ₈	IWB ← WE ← PP	,150	-	Supported
H ₉	IWB ← WE ← I-LC	,161	-	Supported
H ₁₀	IWB ← WE ← E-LC	-.038	-	Rejected

Note: * p ≤ 0.001, ** p ≤ 0.05

As the analysis result, it was determined that the work engagement ($\beta=,150$) had a mediating role in the effect of the proactive personality on the innovative work behavior (lower bounds=,083/upper bounds=,224). Similarly, it was determined that the work engagement ($\beta=,161$) had a mediating role in the effect of the internal locus of control on the innovative work behavior (lower bounds=,095/upper bounds=,232).

However, it was not possible to report that the work engagement ($\beta= -.038$) had a mediating role in the effect of the external locus of control on the innovative work behavior (lower bounds= -.091/upper bounds=,012). Because the confidence interval values included zero (Table 4). As a result, H₈ and H₉ hypotheses were accepted, while the H₁₀ hypothesis was rejected.

5 CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION, AND SUGGESTIONS

As a result of the empirical data obtained within the research, most of the ten research hypotheses developed were supported. Unsupported hypotheses were the result of employees' attitudes towards the locus of control. Internal and external environmental factors can affect the ability of enterprises to produce inventive ideas and innovate.

Employees are among the internal environmental factors, and their innovative behaviors are a significant determinant for businesses to improve themselves and gain a competitive advantage (Weiermair, 2004).

The findings of the survey applied to the food and beverage department employees working in hotel businesses have revealed that not only institutional but also individual factors are efficient in the formation of innovative ideas, attitudes, and behaviors in enterprises. For an innovative corporate culture and organizational climate, executives should consider the employees' personal and behavioral characteristics and develop them with appropriate methods and motivational studies.

5.1 Theoretical Implications

Proactive personality and external locus of control, which have been considered as predictor variables within the scope of the research, directly affect the tendency of hotel employees to display innovative business behaviors.

These findings are similar in many respects to the results of the studies conducted on the subject (Giebels et al., 2016; Görmüş, 2019; Kale, 2019; Li et al., 2017; Pelenk, 2018; Basım & Şeşen, 2008; Rum, 2012; Tabak et al., 2010; Töre & Yolal, 2017). Besides, it is seen that the number of empirical studies conducted for the variables of the study has increased in recent years and the variables are still up-to-date today.

Employees' proactive personality traits and internal locus of control also provide a positive effect on their work engagement level. In the Bakker and Demerouti (2008) model discussed in the axis of work engagement, it has been stated that personal resources such as optimism, self-efficacy, endurance, and self-esteem, etc., are influential for the formation of the work engagement. However, it has not been clearly stated that the individuals' personality features affect work engagement. In this context, it is possible to say that proactive personality and internal locus of control are among the personal resources.

Proactive personality is one of the significant individual factors varying employees' behaviors for positive situational changes in organizations. Similarly, some studies show that proactive personality positively affects work engagement (Bakker, Tims & Derks, 2012; Caniels et al., 2017; Dikkers et al., 2010; Lv, Lv, Xu, Ning & Ning 2018; Uncuoğlu Yolcu, 2017; Wang et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2017).

Besides, various studies have demonstrated that the internal locus of control, which is considered a positive personality trait, positively affects work engagement (Betoret, 2013; Chukwuorji et al., 2018; Duve, 2015; Sharma & Sharma, 2015). These findings obtained are similar in many respects to the results of the studies conducted on the subject.

It is statistically accepted that work engagement included in the model as a mediating variable also has a mediating effect. On the other hand, the hotel

employees' work engagement positively affects the innovative business behavior formations.

This result also contributes to the Bakker and Demerouti theoretical model (2008), furthermore proves that innovative work behavior is one of the increased performances as a result of work engagement in a sense.

Besides, recent studies show that work engagement is a determinant in innovative business behavior (Kim & Koo, 2017; Koch et al., 2015; Köroğlu, 2018; Orth & Volmer, 2017; Rao, 2016). In general, work engaged people can be open to innovations in their work and look for opportunities to bring novelty to their business.

The verification of the structural equation modeling established during the research process as a result of the analysis is one of the most important contributions of this study in the theoretical framework. According to the result of the two-stage road analysis, it is seen that proactive personality and internal locus of control, which are two interrelated predictor variables, increase employees' adaptation and tendency to innovative behavior with the mediating effect of work engagement.

5.2 Practical Implications

The qualified labor force, which makes companies superior in competition and makes them different in the eyes of consumers, is a crucial factor in achieving innovative ideas and applications. In this context, proactive personality traits such as prescience, prudence, courage, perfectionism, etc., are among the features that every business wants its employees to possess.

Managers should consider the employees' proactive personality traits and locus of control tendencies at many stages such as training and coaching, starting from personnel selection. Findings show that proactive personality traits and internal locus of control are also efficient factors in employees' dedication of themselves to their jobs.

Deploying dedicated employees having a proactive personality and internal locus of control attributes to tasks requiring innovative behavior can also benefit the development of creative and effective methods and techniques within the business. This situation can positively affect the innovation skills of the enterprises and also facilitate the employees' adaptation to the innovative organizational culture, thanks to the mediating effect of work engagement.

Resistance is the biggest enemy of the policies and practices supporting innovative work behavior and innovative organizational culture within the enterprise. The findings show that highlighting the employees'

proactive aspects and developing their internal locus of control can also reduce the resistance to innovation through work engagement.

From this perspective, the proactive personality and internal locus of control can reduce the employees' possible resistance towards the innovative organizational climate through the mediating role of work engagement. In this way, a moderate environment is provided for both the employees to improve themselves and the organization to reach its goals effectively and productively.

When the subject is viewed from the perspective of the tourism industry, which is the universe of the research, it is necessary to consider the fact that tourists travel not only for vacation but also for different experiences. Therefore, both tourists search for various experiments in the services provided, and enterprises seek alternative services to introduce.

Although the structure of the services offered to tourists is the same, making an unusual presentation can create a new perception. In hotel businesses, the food and beverage employees, who have more contact with customers than other employees, are the most prominent people to create these new perceptions towards the tourist expectations.

The food and beverage department employees are more competent with customer expectations, as they serve customers directly. Therefore, these employees are very confident in their work, can act in foresight in many issues, and can engage in creative activities in line with customer satisfaction by using initiative. Therefore, it can be proposed that managers can get more favorable results for their business when they offer more autonomy and authority to their employees.

According to the neo-classical management theorist C. Argyris, increasing the responsibility area of the person matures him more and allows him to perform useful activities both for himself and for the business.

5.3 Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

Some suggestions have been made for future research considering the results and limitations of the present study. In the tourism sector experiencing intense changes, businesses have to renew themselves continually.

Furthermore, human behavior also can change continuously. Therefore, studies on this subject can be carried out in different destinations and under various conditions. The study was conducted on the food and beverage department employees of hotel enterprises. It is suggested that future studies should be carried out

in the universe of hotel managers, travel agency managers, or other tourism-related partners.

Within the scope of the research, the relationships between the relevant variables were examined and discussed. The difference analysis of the people characteristics in the sample was not included in the study because, it was not found as appropriate for the research purpose.

Also, significant data about the employees' characteristics can be revealed through difference analysis. Besides, determining a limited number of hotel businesses and measuring institutional innovativeness in this way may allow the innovations to be observed more realistically and determine the factors affecting the innovations in more detail.

Finally, along with other personality traits of the employees, psycho-social, behavioral, attitudinal features may be more effective in evaluating the general qualities of individuals who think and act innovatively. While creating productive and innovative teams, managers can make more rational decisions based on plenty of scientifically proven variables.

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